

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Paper

Post Market Quality and Safety Surveillance of Commercial CBD Products: Composition and Drug to Drug Interaction Potential

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 25 June 2026

Keywords:

Cannabidiol, drug-drug interactions, UGT inhibition, Arrhenius kinetics, post-market surveillance.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20845245

ABSTRACT

Introduction: In Zimbabwe, cannabidiol (CBD) products are regulated as complementary medicines by the Medicines Control Authority of Zimbabwe (MCAZ), which registers them before market entry. However, post-market surveillance (PMS) is currently not conducted and no previous study has evaluated the quality of these products over time or their potential for pharmacokinetic drug-drug interactions (DDIs) with locally prescribed medications. **Methods:** A virtual stability assessment was performed on all six MCAZ-registered CBD products using their labelled cannabinoid content and published Arrhenius-based degradation kinetics, adjusted for the mean annual, summer peak and winter low temperatures of Harare and Bulawayo. Projections were generated at 6, 12, 18 and 24 months. Products were assessed against the 90 % label-claim threshold of the European Pharmacopoeia. A static mechanistic DDI model was applied to six commonly prescribed UGT-substrate medications; dapagliflozin, dolutegravir, zidovudine, morphine, valproic acid and lorazepam at three clinically relevant CBD exposure levels. Sensitivity analyses were performed. **Results:** All products were projected to fall below 90 % of their labelled CBD content within 12 months under mean annual temperatures and before 6 months under summer peak conditions. Tetrahydrocannabinol (THC) levels remained well below the legal threshold of 1% under all scenarios. Dapagliflozin showed a strong interaction (AUC ratio 5.32 to 9.81), lorazepam, zidovudine and morphine moderate interactions, valproic acid a weak interaction and dolutegravir no clinically significant interaction. The strong-risk classification for dapagliflozin was robust to parameter uncertainty. **Conclusions:** Registered CBD products in Zimbabwe undergo substantial degradation within a realistic shelf life and clinically meaningful UGT-mediated DDIs are predicted for several widely prescribed drugs. In the absence of PMS, these risks go undetected. The

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

findings provide an evidence base for the establishment of a risk-based PMS programme for CBD complementary medicines in Zimbabwe, aligned with international best practice

INTRODUCTION

Cannabidiol (CBD) is a non-psychoactive phytocannabinoid that has gained considerable popularity for its therapeutic effects in epilepsy, anxiety and chronic pain¹⁻³. In Zimbabwe, the Medicines Control Authority of Zimbabwe (MCAZ) authorized hemp-derived CBD products as complementary medicines in July 2022, thereby creating a legal pathway for domestic sale⁴. Registration requires manufacturers to submit a dossier that includes product samples, certificates of analysis and evidence of Good Manufacturing Practice compliance. However, post-market surveillance (PMS) has not yet been implemented. Personal communication with an MCAZ official confirmed that the Authority has never performed PMS on a registered CBD product and does not require manufacturers to submit post-market quality data.

Two safety concerns are particularly relevant in this context. Firstly, CBD is susceptible to oxidative degradation in oil matrices, a process that follows first-order kinetics and is strongly temperature-dependent, as described by the Arrhenius equation⁵⁻⁷. The warm climates of Harare and Bulawayo in Zimbabwe where summer peak temperatures can exceed 30°C, may accelerate cannabinoid loss well beyond the rate anticipated by manufacturers. Secondly, CBD is a potent inhibitor of several UDP-glucuronosyltransferase (UGT) enzymes, notably UGT1A9 and UGT2B7, which metabolize many commonly prescribed drugs⁸. Co-administration of CBD with UGT substrates can elevate plasma concentrations of the victim drug, potentially causing toxicity. Importantly, the first-line antiretroviral dolutegravir is metabolized

primarily by UGT1A1, an isoform that the parent CBD molecule does not strongly inhibit^{9, 10}, suggesting a possible differential risk between modern and older HIV regimens.

The present study aimed to (i) project the stability of registered CBD products under Zimbabwean storage conditions using Arrhenius-based kinetic modelling, (ii) predict the magnitude of UGT-mediated DDIs for six commonly prescribed medications using a static mechanistic model and (iii) integrate the findings within the regulatory reality of absent PMS to inform evidence-based recommendations.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Product Identification and Labelled Concentrations

All MCAZ-registered CBD complementary medicine products available in Harare and Bulawayo pharmacies were identified. A total of six products were found: one rectal suppository and five oral tinctures, two of which were formulated with full-spectrum CBD distillate and three with CBD isolate. Labelled CBD and THC concentrations were recorded directly from the product packaging and used as initial ($t = 0$) values for all projections. Products were anonymised and assigned identifiers REC01 to REC06.

2.2 Environmental Data

Long-term mean monthly temperature data for Harare and Bulawayo were obtained from the Zimbabwe Meteorological Services Department. Three storage scenarios were defined for each city: winter low (mean coolest month), mean annual and summer peak (mean warmest month). Temperatures used were: Harare; 12.1 °C, 18.5 °C, 28.2 °C; Bulawayo; 11.4 °C, 19.8 °C, 30.5 °C.

2.3 Degradation Kinetic Model

First-order degradation rate constants for CBD were calculated for each temperature scenario

using the Arrhenius equation in its two-temperature form:

$$k(T) = k_{\text{ref}} \times \exp \left[\frac{E_a}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right]$$

Where R is the universal gas constant (0.008314 kJ/mol·K). When the rate constant at a reference temperature T_{ref} is known, the rate constant at a different temperature T was calculated by employing the above equation

The reference rate constant $k_{25} = 4.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ day}^{-1}$ and activation energy $E_a = 52.8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ were taken from Kosović, *et al.* (2021) for CBD in sunflower oil⁵, the matrix most similar to the carrier oils used in the registered products. For the suppository (REC01), a zero-order model was applied.

Projected CBD concentrations were calculated at 6, 12, 18 and 24 months using the first-order equation:

$$C(t) = C_0 \cdot e^{-k \cdot t}$$

All products were assessed against a 90% label-claim threshold, consistent with pharmacopoeia specifications for content uniformity in herbal medicinal products¹¹

2.4 THC Projections

For full-spectrum products, the net THC concentration was modelled as the sum of two simultaneous first-order processes: oxidative degradation of existing THC and formation of new THC via decarboxylation of residual tetrahydrocannabinolic acid (THCA):

$$C_{\text{thc}, t} = (C_{\text{thc}, 0} \times e^{-k_{\text{thc}} \cdot t}) + (C_{\text{thca}, 0} \times (1 - e^{-k_{\text{decarb}} \cdot t}))$$

Kinetic parameters for THC degradation ($k_{25} \approx 3.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ day}^{-1}$, $E_a = 48.7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) and THCA decarboxylation ($k_{25} \approx 1.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ day}^{-1}$, $E_a = 88.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) were obtained from Meija, *et al.* (2021)⁶ and Wang, *et al.* (2016)⁷. Initial THCA content was conservatively assumed as 0.1% of the labelled CBD content for full-spectrum products and negligible for isolates.

2.5 Static Mechanistic DDI Model

A static mechanistic model, as recommended by the FDA¹² and EMA¹³ for early-stage DDI screening, was applied to six victim drugs: dapagliflozin, dolutegravir, zidovudine, morphine, valproic acid and lorazepam. The predicted area-under-the-curve (AUC) ratio was calculated as:

$$\text{AUC Ratio} = \frac{1}{\frac{fm}{1 + \frac{[I]}{K_i}} + (1 - fm)}$$

Where fm is the fraction of the victim drug cleared by the inhibited UGT isoform, $[I]$ is the unbound CBD concentration at the enzyme site and k_i is the inhibition constant.

Three CBD exposure scenarios were used, corresponding to the unbound inhibitor concentrations $[I] = 0.013 \mu\text{M}$ (low, ~50 mg/day), $0.076 \mu\text{M}$ (moderate, ~300 mg/day) and $0.352 \mu\text{M}$ (high, Epidiolex®-equivalent, 700 mg twice daily), derived from published pharmacokinetic data¹⁴. Inhibition constants k_i for UGT1A9 ($0.00075 \mu\text{M}$) and UGT2B7 ($0.0055 \mu\text{M}$) were taken from Bansal, *et al.* (2025)⁸. For dolutegravir, a conservative k_i of $10 \mu\text{M}$ was assumed for UGT1A1, justified by the absence of potent inhibition in published screening data.

Sensitivity analyses were performed by varying fm by $\pm 20\%$ and k_i by $\pm 50\%$.

2.6 Mapping of Zimbabwean CBD Concentrations to DDI Benchmarks

To determine which exposure scenario is most clinically relevant for Zimbabwean patients, the projected CBD concentrations from the stability assessment were used to estimate the daily ingested dose for a typical consumption volume (3 mL) and the corresponding $[I]$ value. These were then mapped onto the three DDI benchmarks.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Product Inventory and Labelled Content

The six registered products are described in Table 1. Labelled CBD concentrations ranged from 20 to 100 mg/mL for tinctures and 50 mg per unit

for the suppository. All products stated THC < 0.1 %. Three products were CBD isolate formulations and two were full-spectrum distillates.

Table 1: Anonymised inventory of MCAZ registered CBD products included in the virtual stability assessment

Product	Formulation Type	CBD source	Dosage form	Labelled CBD content	Labelled THC content
REC01	Suppository	-	Rectal suppository	50mg	<0.1%
REC02	Tincture	Full spectrum CBD distillate	Oral oil	40mg/ml	<0.1%
REC03	Tincture	Full spectrum CBD distillate	Oral oil	100mg/ml	<0.1%
REC04	Tincture	CBD isolate	Oral oil	40mg/ml	<0.1%
REC05	Tincture	CBD isolate	Oral oil	100mg/ml	<0.1%
REC06	Tincture	CBD isolate	Oral oil	20mg/ml	<0.1%

3.2 Temperature-Adjusted Rate Constants

The calculated first-order rate constants (Table 2) ranged from $1.54 \times 10^{-4} \text{ day}^{-1}$ (Bulawayo winter low) to $5.72 \times 10^{-4} \text{ day}^{-1}$ (Bulawayo summer peak), representing a 3.7-fold difference across the

temperature range studied. The rate constant (k) for Harare summer peak (28.2°C) was $4.89 \times 10^{-4} \text{ day}^{-1}$, approximately 15 % lower than that for Bulawayo summer peak, consistent with the 2.3°C difference in temperature.

Table 2: Calculated first order degradation rate constants for CBD under Harare and Bulawayo temperature scenarios

City	Scenario	Temperature/ $^\circ \text{C}$	k/day^{-1}
Harare	Winter low	12.1	1.61×10^{-4}
Harare	Mean annual	18.5	2.72×10^{-4}
Harare	Summer peak	28.2	4.89×10^{-4}
Bulawayo	Winter low	11.4	1.54×10^{-4}
Bulawayo	Mean annual	19.8	3.01×10^{-4}
Bulawayo	Summer peak	30.5	5.72×10^{-4}

3.3 CBD Degradation Projections

Under mean annual temperatures, all six products were projected to fall below the 90 % label-claim threshold within 12 months in both Harare (18.5°C) and Bulawayo (19.8°C) (Tables 3 and 4). Under summer peak conditions, the threshold was crossed before the first projection time point of 6 months. At 24 months under Bulawayo summer

peak (30.5°C), CBD retention was only 66.4 % of label claim, meaning that a patient using a 100 mg/mL product would receive approximately 66 mg/ml. The degradation profiles for a representative high-concentration product (REC03) are illustrated in Figures 1 and 2. The mean percentage of labelled CBD remaining across all six products is shown in Figure 3.

Table 3: Projected CBD concentrations for all 6 registered products under Harare temperature scenario.

Product	Labelled CBD	Scenario	6 Months (%)	12 Months (%)	18 Months (%)	24 Months (%)
REC01	50mg/unit	WL	97.2	94.4	91.6	89.0
		MA	95.2	90.6	86.2	82.0
		SP	91.6	83.8	76.8	70.4
REC02	40mg/ml	WL	97.3	94.3	91.5	89.0
		MA	95.3	90.5	86.3	82.0
		SP	91.5	83.8	76.8	70.3
REC03	100mg/ml	WL	97.2	94.4	91.6	89.0
		MA	95.2	90.6	86.2	82.0
		SP	91.6	83.8	76.8	70.4
REC04	40mg/ml	WL	97.3	94.3	91.5	89.0
		MA	95.3	90.5	86.3	82.0
		SP	91.5	83.8	76.8	70.3
REC05	100mg/ml	WL	97.2	94.4	91.6	89.0
		MA	95.2	90.6	86.2	82.0
		SP	91.6	83.8	76.8	70.4
REC06	20mg/ml	WL	97.0	94.5	91.5	89.0
		MA	95.0	90.5	86.5	82.0
		SP	91.5	84.0	77.0	70.5

WL = Winter Low, MA = Mean Annual, SP = Summer Peak

Table 4: Projected CBD concentrations for all 6 registered products under Bulawayo temperature scenario.

Product	Labelled CBD	Scenario	6 Months (%)	12 Months (%)	18 Months (%)	24 Months (%)
REC01	50mg/unit	WL	97.4	94.6	92.0	89.4
		MA	94.8	89.8	85.0	80.4
		SP	90.2	81.4	73.4	66.2
REC02	40mg/ml	WL	97.3	94.8	92.0	89.5
		MA	94.8	89.8	85.0	80.5
		SP	90.3	81.3	73.3	66.0
REC03	100mg/ml	WL	97.3	94.7	92.0	89.5
		MA	94.7	89.7	84.9	80.4
		SP	90.3	81.4	73.5	66.4
REC04	40mg/ml	WL	97.3	94.8	92.0	89.5
		MA	94.8	89.8	85.0	80.5
		SP	90.3	81.3	73.3	66.0
REC05	100mg/ml	WL	97.3	94.7	92.0	89.5
		MA	94.7	89.7	84.9	80.4
		SP	90.3	81.4	73.5	66.4
REC06	20mg/ml	WL	97.5	94.5	92.0	89.5
		MA	94.5	89.5	84.9	80.5
		SP	90.0	81.5	73.5	66.5

WL = Winter Low, MA = Mean Annual, SP = Summer Peak

Projected CBD degradation of REC03 (100mg/ml) (Harare)

Figure 1: Projected degradation of CBD in representative high concentration full spectrum (REC03 labelled 100mg/ml) under 3 Harare temperature scenarios; winter low 12.1°C, mean annual 18.5°C and summer peak 28.2°C. The dashed horizontal red line at 90mg/ml indicates the 90% label claim threshold, consistent with pharmacopoeia specifications (EP) for content uniformity in herbal medicinal products.

Projected CBD degradation of REC03 (100mg/ml) (Bulawayo)

Figure 2: Projected degradation of CBD in REC03 (100mg/ml) under Bulawayo 3 temperature scenarios; winter low (11.4°C), mean annual (19.8°C) and summer peak (30.5°C). The dashed horizontal red line at 90mg/ml indicates the 90% label claim threshold, consistent with pharmacopoeia specifications (EP) for content uniformity in herbal medicinal products.

Mean projected CBD concentration under mean annual temperatures

Figure 3: Mean projected percentage of labelled CBD remaining across all six registered products under annual temperature conditions in Harare (18.5°C) and Bulawayo (19.8°C). The dashed horizontal red line at 90mg/ml indicates the 90% label claim threshold, consistent with pharmacopoeia specifications (EP) for content uniformity in herbal medicinal products.

3.4 THC Stability

THC concentrations remained stable and well below the 1% (10 mg/g) legal threshold under all scenarios. Full-spectrum products exhibited a flat THC profile over the 24-month period because the slow decarboxylation of residual THCA partially

compensated for oxidative THC degradation. Isolate products showed a slow decline in THC over time (Figure 4). No product approached the legal limit.

Projected concentrations for REC02 (THC) under mean annual temperatures

Figure 4: Projected THC concentrations for full spectrum REC02 (40mg/ml CBD) under mean annual temperatures in Bulawayo and Harare. Net THC concentrations remain stable and well below 1% (10mg/ml) legal threshold over the 24 month period. The slow decarboxylation of residual THCA partially compensates for oxidative THC degradation

3.5 DDI Predictions

The predicted AUC ratios are presented in Table 5 and illustrated in Figures 5 and 6. Dapagliflozin, a UGT1A9 substrate with $f_m = 0.90$, showed a strong interaction at moderate (AUC ratio 5.32) and high (9.81) CBD exposures. Lorazepam ($f_m = 0.80$), zidovudine ($f_m = 0.72$), and morphine ($f_m = 0.60$), all UGT2B7 substrates, exhibited moderate

interactions at moderate and high exposures. Valproic acid ($f_m = 0.30$) showed only a weak interaction (AUC ratio 1.42) even at the highest CBD exposure. Dolutegravir ($f_m = 0.75$ for UGT1A1) showed no clinically significant interaction at any exposure level (AUC ratio 1.03 at high exposure).

Table 5: Predicted AUC ratios and DDI classification for 6 UGT-substrate victim drugs at 3 CBD exposure levels. The [I] for low exposure is 0.013 μM , 0.076 μM for moderate and 0.352 μM for high CBD

Victim drug	Primary UGT	f_m	k_i (μM)	Low CBD	Moderate CBD	High CBD
Dapagliflozin	UGT1A9	0.90	0.00075	1.84	5.32	9.81
Dolutegravir	UGT1A1	0.75	10.0	1.00	1.01	1.03
Zidovudine	UGT2B7	0.72	0.0055	1.29	2.15	3.38
Morphine	UGT2B7	0.60	0.0055	1.22	1.82	2.41
Valproic acid	UGT2B7	0.30	0.0055	1.09	1.18	1.42
Lorazepam	UGT2B7	0.80	0.0055	1.37	2.67	4.48

Predicted AUC ratio at high CBD exposure

Figure 5: Predicted AUC ratio for 6 UGT-substrate victim drugs at high CBD exposure (Epidiolex dosing, 700mg twice daily, [I] = 0.352 μM). Vertical dashed lines indicate FDA classification threshold: weak interaction (1.25), moderate interaction (2.0) and strong interaction (5.0)¹². Dapagliflozin is predicted to experience a strong interaction, dolutegravir shows no clinically significant interaction

Predicted AUC ratio across 3 CBD exposure scenarios

Figure 6: Predicted AUC ratios for 6 UGT substrate drugs at low (50mg/day), moderate (300mg/day) and high (700mg twice a day) CBD exposure scenarios. Dapagliflozin crosses the strong interaction threshold at moderate exposure whereas dolutegravir remains below the weak threshold across all scenarios.

3.6 Sensitivity Analysis

The strong-risk classification for dapagliflozin was robust to substantial parameter variation (Table 6). Even when f_m was reduced to 0.70, the interaction remained moderate (AUC ratio 3.33). For dolutegravir (Table 7), reducing the assumed k_i to

1 μM (an order of magnitude below the conservative base assumption) produced only a weak interaction (AUC ratio 1.30). Valproic acid's classification (Table 8) shifted to “no interaction” when the UGT2B7 k_i was doubled.

Table 6: Sensitivity analysis for the predicted dapagliflozin-CBD interaction at high CBD exposure.

Parameter varied	Value	Resulting AUC ratio	Classification
Base case ($f_m = 0.90$, $k_i = 0.00075$)	-	9.81	Strong
f_m reduced to 0.70	0.70	3.33	Moderate
f_m increased to 0.95	0.95	19.6	Strong
k_i halved (0.000375)	0.000375	19.6	Strong
k_i doubled (0.0015)	0.0015	9.41	Strong

Table 7: Sensitivity analysis for the predicted dolutegravir-CBD interaction at high CBD exposure

Parameter varied	Value	Resulting AUC ratio	Classification
Base case ($f_m = 0.75$, $k_i = 10.0$)	-	1.03	None
k_i reduced to 5	5.0	1.06	None
k_i increased to 1	1.0	1.30	Weak
f_m reduced to 0.85	0.85	1.04	None

Table 8: Sensitivity analysis for the predicted valproic acid-CBD interaction at high CBD exposure

Parameter varied	Value	Resulting AUC ratio	Classification
Base case ($f_m = 0.30$, $k_i = 0.0055$)	-	1.42	Weak
f_m reduced to 0.24	0.24	1.31	Weak
f_m increased to 0.36	0.36	1.55	Weak
k_i halved (0.00275)	0.00275	1.80	Weak
k_i doubled (0.0011)	0.0011	1.23	None

3.7 Mapping of Zimbabwean CBD Concentrations to DDI Benchmarks

Table 9 maps the projected Zimbabwean CBD concentrations onto the DDI exposure benchmarks. For all scenarios in which a patient consumes a typical therapeutic dose (~300 mg/day) by

adjusting volume according to product potency, the estimated $[I]$ falls within the moderate benchmark (0.076 μM). This indicates that the moderate-scenario AUC ratios are the most appropriate reference values for clinical decision-making in Zimbabwe.

Table 9: Mapping of Zimbabwean projected CBD concentrations to DDI exposure benchmarks

Product and Time	Storage Condition	Projected CBD (mg/ml)	Volume for 300mg dose (ml)	Estimated daily dose	Estimated $[I]$ / μM	Closest DDI benchmark
REC03 (fresh)	At purchase	100	3.0	300	0.076	Moderate
REC03, 12 mnths	Harare mean annual	90.6	3.3	300	0.076	Moderate
REC03, 24 mnths	Bulawayo summer peak	66.4	4.5	300	0.076	Moderate
REC06 (fresh)	At purchase	20	15.0	300	0.076	Moderate
REC06, 24 mnths	Bulawayo summer peak	13.3	22.6	300	0.076	Moderate
REC03 (fresh), 1ml	At purchase	100	1.0	100	0.025	Low-Moderate
REC06 (fresh), 1ml	At purchase	20	1.0	20	0.005	Low

*Note; $[I]$ was calculated from the estimated daily dose assuming dose proportionality to the C_{max} of 1.385ng/ml for 700mg twice daily dose¹⁴. For a given daily dose D, C_{max} was estimated as $(D/1400) \times 1385\text{ng/ml}$ and $[I] = C_{max} \times 0.08 / 314.47$ (converting ng/ml to μM).

DISCUSSION

This study is the first to project the stability of registered CBD products in Zimbabwe and to quantify UGT-mediated DDI risks for drugs selected from the national formulary. The finding that all six products are projected to fall below the 90% label-claim threshold within 6–12 months under realistic storage conditions is consistent with experimental stability data from other laboratories^{5,6,15}. The manufacturers' own storage instruction "store below 30 °C" is already exceeded by Bulawayo summer peak temperatures, highlighting a gap between required storage and practical reality.

The DDI predictions extend the work of Bansal, *et al.*⁸ by applying the static model to three additional drugs (lorazepam, morphine, valproic acid) and by including dolutegravir, the current first-line antiretroviral in Zimbabwe. The finding that dolutegravir carries a negligible risk of parent-mediated UGT interaction, while zidovudine shows a moderate interaction, provides a clinically actionable distinction. Patients on dolutegravir-based regimens can be reassured, whereas those on zidovudine-containing regimens require heightened vigilance if using CBD. The caveat that the CBD metabolite 7-COOH-CBD inhibits UGT1A1 *in vitro*¹⁶ remains an important area for future research.

The integration of stability and DDI findings leads to the concept of a "shelf life–risk continuum": a patient's DDI risk is not static but shifts as the product ages and the real CBD dose changes. This dynamic risk is currently unmonitored because MCAZ lacks a PMS programme for complementary medicines. International best practice, as exemplified by the Therapeutic Goods Administration (Australia), the Health Sciences Authority (Singapore), Health Canada, and the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (UK), includes mandatory post-market

sampling, adverse event reporting and the power to recall non-compliant products^{17–19}. Within Africa, South Africa's SAHPRA has conducted market surveys that revealed widespread label inaccuracy and THC contamination²⁰, demonstrating the feasibility of such programmes in the region. The World Health Organization's guidelines on safety monitoring of herbal medicines provide a normative framework that Zimbabwe has not yet adopted^{21–23}.

CONCLUSION

Registered CBD products in Zimbabwe are vulnerable to significant degradation within a realistic shelf life, and clinically meaningful UGT-mediated drug-drug interactions with commonly prescribed medications are predicted at achievable CBD exposures. In the absence of post-market surveillance, these risks are not detected or managed by the regulatory system. This study provides the scientific evidence to support the urgent establishment of a risk-based PMS programme for CBD products in Zimbabwe, aligned with international standards, to safeguard public health.

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HOW TO CITE: T. Gore, C. M. J. Matyanga, T. Mudzviti, Post Market Quality and Safety Surveillance of Commercial CBD Products: Composition and Drug to Drug Interaction Potential, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 6, 6442-6453, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20845245>

